

Seven Events that Shaped the New Testament World by Carter¹

Book Review:

Warren Carter's 'Seven Events...'

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(1) Seven events that are significant for understanding the New Testament writings:

***Chapter One:*²**

“In a gentle manner the problems associated with separating ‘fact’ from ‘legend’ are mentioned by appealing to Oliver Stone’s cinematic representation. For Carter, it is Alexander’s impact that creates a legacy that is relevant for the New Testament.”³ More broadly, however, this event marked the beginning of the Hellenistic period, during which Greek culture, philosophy, language, and diversity spread throughout the Mediterranean world: a “buffet” in which the Jesus movement was born into.⁴ The main theme is that Alexander’s life and legacy contributed to this phenomenon.⁵

¹ Warren Carter, *Seven Events That Shaped the New Testament World* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2013).

² Carter, *Seven Events*, “The Death of Alexander the Great (323 BCE),” 1 – 20.

³ Paul Foster, “Seven Events for Understanding The New Testament (Review),” *The Expository Times* 125, no. 3 (December 2013), 137.

⁴ Carter, *Seven Events*, 16.

⁵ Carter, *Seven Events*, 1 – 20.

Chapter Two:⁶

Known as the Septuagint, this translation made the Hebrew scriptures accessible to Greek-speaking Jews and Gentiles. It played a crucial role in the spread of Judaism and the development of early Christianity, and, essentially, “a source of theological vocabulary for the early Jesus movement.”⁷ However, this chapter is a prime example of Carter’s skill in utilising his book’s structure to segue between key events, such as his approach to the Septuagint by examining the *Letter of Aristeas*. He utilises the “Septuagint as a means of presenting the reader with the concept of the Hellenization of the Jews.”⁸ Jews were adapting to Hellenization at the same time as trying to ensure their *Jewishness*, culturally and religiously.⁹

Chapter Three:¹⁰

Carter’s reference to this *Rededication* reveals tension of faithfulness within the Jewish community that aligns with modern day dilemmas of a similar nature.¹¹ However, the significance of such rededication speaks to the importance of the negotiation of Greek culture into Jewish faith and diverse customs, and, ultimately, how we can locate the Jewish figures of Jesus and Paul in the vibrant kaleidoscope and mingling of customs and beliefs.¹²

⁶ Carter, *Seven Events*, “The Process of Translating Hebrew Scriptures into Greek (ca. 250 BCE),” 21 – 42.

⁷ Carter, *Seven Events*, 41.

⁸ J. R. McConnell, J. R. “Book Review: Warren Carter, *Seven Events that Shaped the New Testament World*,” *Review & Expositor*, 112, no. 2 (2015), 328. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0034637315582479c>.

⁹ Mitzi J. Smith and Suk Kim, *Toward Decentring The New Testament: A Reintroduction* (Eugene, OR: Cascade Books, 2008), 31; Mark Allan Powell, *Introducing The New Testament: A Historical, Literary, and Theological Survey (Second Edition)* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2009), 54.

¹⁰ Carter, *Seven Events*, “The Rededication of the Jerusalem Temple (164 BCE),” 43 – 64.

¹¹ Paul Foster, “Seven Events,” 138.

¹² Smith & Kim, *Toward Decentring*, 31 – 34.

Chapter Four:¹³

The Roman Empire's control over Judea had a significant impact on the political and social context in which the New Testament writings emerged. It influenced the religious landscape, shaped the socio-economic conditions, and set the stage for the conflicts between Jesus and the religious authorities.¹⁴ Focusing on a lavish narrative of the eastern Mediterranean, Carter showcases Roman colonization, empire, and the resistance that occurred from 63 BCE.

Also discussed was the Herodian collaboration with the Romans and their efforts to maintain power created tensions and conflicts that are reflected in the New Testament writings,¹⁵ creating an environment that would eventually divide Rabbinic Judaism from predominantly Gentile Christianity.¹⁶

Chapter Five:¹⁷

New Testament territory is arrived at temporally and spiritually in this chapter. The rise of early Christianity, from its origins in the ministry of Jesus to its spread throughout the Roman Empire, is a central event that shaped the New Testament world. The teachings of Jesus, the missionary efforts of the apostles, and the formation of Christian communities all contributed to the development of the New Testament writings. Obvious to many is the tremendous historical and theological ramifications of Jesus' Crucifixion; however, Carter is clear in explaining the Crucifixion in terms of its placement in "wider socio-political forces at work in the Empire."¹⁸

¹³ Carter, *Seven Events*, "The Roman Occupation of Judea (63 BCE)," 65 – 85.

¹⁴ Also see Smith & Kim, *Toward Decentring*, 31 – 34; and Powell, *Introducing The NT*, 17 – 37.

¹⁵ Carter, *Seven Events*, 69 – 74.

¹⁶ Although not elaborated on by Carter, for context, a more thorough discussion can be found in Smith and Kim, *Toward Decentring*, 33 – 35.

¹⁷ Carter, *Seven Events*, "The Crucifixion of Jesus (ca. 30 CE)," 87 – 106.

¹⁸ Foster, "Seven Events," 138; Carter's mater could have extended with respect to this chapter to better assist readers locate inextricable links between the early chapters and chapter five. One such article (and the

Chapters Six and Seven:¹⁹

Carter's final two chapters are closely linked, and text and textuality are elevated by Carter at these points in history because of their inextricable connection to the growth and advancement of Christian ideas.²⁰ Carter uses clear and concise language to convey some heavy insights that may not be apparent to parts of the law community. For instance, redaction of the gospels, the timespan in which the relevant text took place, and the rationality of processing text that could almost seem *unholy*. In his final chapter, Carter crescendos towards Athanasius' pivotal letter (367 CE), providing the leading known original list of 27 New Testament writings, finding official church ratification in the Council of Carthage in 397 CE.²¹ Carter leaves his readers with an upbeat reflection of canonisation; that it indeed legitimated diversity and multiplicity that can be delivered in a contemporary context.²²

(2) Historical, religious, socio-cultural, and political contexts of the New Testament, with respect to Hellenistic influence, Jewish traditions, and Roman imperial power:

(a) Hellenistic Influence:

Carter's exploration of the Hellenistic period and its impact on the New Testament world helps deepen an understanding of the cultural and philosophical milieu in which the New Testament writings were produced. The spread of Greek language and culture, the influence of Hellenistic philosophy, and the interaction between Greek and Jewish thought all shaped the ideas and language used in the New Testament.

book it reviews), when combined with Carter's material, are quite helpful: Zeba A. Crook, "The Historical Jesus of the Gospels by Craig S. Keener (Review)," *Toronto Journal of Theology*, 30, no. 2 (Fall 2014), 320 – 322.

¹⁹ Carter, *Seven Events*, "The Writings of the New Testaments Texts (ca. 50-ca. 130 CE)" 107 – 132; and, "The Process of "Closing" the New Testament Canon (397 CE)," 133 – 157.

²⁰ Arguments that are fully verified by publications such as by Luke Timothy Johnson, *Becoming the New Testament: The New Testament: A Very Short Introduction* (New York: Oxford Academic, 2010), <https://doi.org/10.1093/actrade/9780199735709.003.0010>.

²¹ Carter, *Seven Events*, 147 – 150.

²² Carter, *Seven Events*, 154.

(b) Jewish Traditions:

Carter's examination of Jewish traditions, including the translation of the Hebrew Bible into Greek has shed light on the religious and cultural context in which the New Testament writings emerged. Understanding the Jewish background, influence, and indeed, tensions with the New Testament help to interpret its teachings and themes more accurately.

(c) Roman Imperial Power:

Carter's analysis of the Roman occupation of Judea and the political dynamics of the time enhances understanding of the socio-political context in which the New Testament writings were written. The Roman Empire's control over Judea, its influence on religious institutions, and the conflicts between Jesus and the Roman authorities all contribute to a deeper understanding of the New Testament.

(3) Strengths/Weaknesses:

Carter's book has several strengths, including its comprehensive exploration of the historical, religious, socio-cultural, and political contexts of the New Testament. The author provides a detailed analysis of each of the seven events and their significance, offering a nuanced understanding of the world behind the New Testament.

At first sight, in chapters four to seven, readers may have expected to see how Hellenistic culture and Greek language affected the Roman control of Judea, Jesus' Crucifixion, the production of the New Testament texts, and canon creation. In chapters six and seven, readers may have preferred a presentation of the available textual materials or documents that show how transmission occurred and how we eventually arrived at our New Testament text rather than a general discussion of the well-known process of canon formation based on traditions. For these reasons, perhaps it may be argued that the work

fails to substantially add to the available knowledge of the New Testament context.²³

However, there is method in Carter's colloquial style, reminding the reader of someone who wishes to impart precious (and important) knowledge at their level, who does not stand from a position of self-righteousness.²⁴

To ignite, inspire, and include audiences who may not otherwise have engaged with this material is a wonderful gift given by Carter. More than *just* a "helpful aid,"²⁵ Carter's book succeeds in providing a window onto the world behind the New Testament by offering a comprehensive exploration of the historical, religious, socio-cultural, and political contexts for a broad spectrum of communities.

²³ Hughson Ong, "Review: CARTER Seven Events," *Journal of Greco-Roman Christianity and Judaism*, no. 9 (2018), 103.

²⁴ Opinions of fellow theologians and religious scholars who seek to criticise his pedagogical misgivings and colloquial conversationalist tone, whilst conceding Carter's superior mastery of relevant history are unfair. For instance, see Robert G. T. Edwards, "Warren Carter. Seven Events that Shaped the New Testament World. Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2013 (Review)," *Toronto Journal of Theology*, 30, No. 2 (Fall 2014), 319 - 320.

²⁵ Edwards, "Warren Carter," 319.

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